

E7.2 Market and Business Opportunities Analysis v1.0

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[6GENABLERS-DLT]
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

5G	5 th Generation
6G	6 th Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
BDS	Big Data & Security
BFSI	Banking, Financial Services and Insurance
BSS	Business Support Systems
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
CLI	Command Line Interface
CSP	Communication Service Provider
dApp	decentralized Application
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
Dev	Development
DeFi	Decentralized Finance
DPoS	Delegated Proof of Stake
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
EU	European Union
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JU	Joint Undertaking
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KVI	Key Value Indicator
MANO	MANagement and Orchestration
MCS	Mission Critical Systems
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NS	Network Service
OSM	Open Source MANO
OSS	Operational Support Systems
PoA	Proof of Activity
PoS	Proof of Stake
PoW	Proof of Work
QoS	Quality of Service
R&D	Research and Development
SC	Smart Contract

SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SD	Smart Discovery
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organizations
SME	Small & Medium Enterprise
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
T&C	Terms and conditions
TMT	Telecom, Media & Technology
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
uRLLC	ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications
US	United States
USD	US Dollar
VM	Virtual Machine

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E7.2 Market and Business Opportunities Analysis*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). With the first version of the core pieces, building the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace, developed and integrated, this document describes the planned activities for exploitation to be done during the project and beyond the project lifetime. The objective of this document is to provide a Market and Business Opportunities Analysis in the context of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. First, a market analysis is performed to understand the context in which the 6G networks are starting to be defined and how new technologies, like blockchain and Smart Contracts, can help to cope with the demanding requirements that will be imposed to the future telco networks. Thereafter, once the Key Exploitable Results have been identified, a business analysis is conducted, which enables the identification of business models. Finally, the exploitation possibilities are presented to conclude with an overall assessment of the project impact. In essence, this deliverable specifies, for each identified project exploitable results or assets, the potential business models and plans, the exploitation strategy to be followed and the impact assessment to track and evaluate the economic influence of the results in the entity developing the solution.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The present document stresses the business and exploitation plans for the developed DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace, i.e. the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, including indicators to achieve and keep track.

To do that, common methodologies and practices analyze the potential and plan the activities that will be performed. Those are compiled in this document, including different canvases to span different corners and perspectives, and specific strategies driven to contribute to the metrics targeted.

This way, the objectives to accomplish are:

1. Identify individual assets and results with relevance to exploit.
2. Outline the business opportunities envisioned for the different outcomes and knowledge resulting from the implementation of the developed components.
3. Describe the strategy to follow to perform exploitation at different levels or paths which will mean specific activities.
4. Envision the goals to assess the success of the activities and ground the business expectations from the results.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable constitutes a key outcome of Work Package 7 (P7 – Impact Creation) of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. This work package focuses on the promotion of results of the project in scientific and industrial fora to stakeholders. Then, P7 puts emphasis on the definition of an exploitation strategy to analyze its market intentions, while ensuring alignment with the roadmap of Horizon Europe (HE) Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) actions. In this context, this document provides the details of the analysis of market and business opportunities and exploitation strategies triggered from the initial prototype implementation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E7.2 is the joint result of all the tasks within P7, which are outlined below:

- ❖ A7.1: This task supports the development of targeted dissemination and communication of the DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace for 6G, with a focus on maximizing visibility and outreach. It defines strategic communication priorities, identifies target audiences, crafts key messages and statements, determines strategic communication channels, and establishes a time plan for communication activities.
- ❖ A7.2: This task covers the dissemination of project outcomes related to the DLT testbed, ensuring they reach a wide academic, industrial, and business audience. It aims to synchronize with relevant discussions in standardization bodies to gather feedback for the execution of technical tasks.
- ❖ A7.3: This task focuses on disseminating project outcomes related to Smart Contracts-enabled negotiation, targeting academic, industrial, and business audiences. Similarly,

it aims to synchronize with relevant standardization discussions to gather feedback and potential contributions.

❖ A7.4: This task deals with the dissemination of project outcomes related to the Service Level Agreement (SLA) assurance, ensuring they reach a broad academic, industrial, and business audience. It also aims to synchronize with relevant standardization discussions to gather feedback and potential contributions.

Figure 1-1 E7.2 positioning and relation to the project's activities

The implemented systems, reported in E3.2 [1], E4.2 [2] and E5.2 [3], build the initial prototypes for the Distributed Telco Marketplace envisioned in the project. From these results, A7.2 analyses the business perspectives.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section provides an overview of the document, including its objectives, the relationship to the project's activities, and the structure of the document itself.
- Section 2: This section introduces the 6th Generation (6G) market context and needs and presents the state of the art to zoom on the market needs that solutions are trying to meet.
- Section 3: This section presents market analysis, by identifying the market potential and main related players.

- Section 4: This section provides the business models and plans of the targeted assets and knowledge, applying different canvas methodologies.
- Section 5: This section presents the exploitation strategies designed based on the identified Key Exploitable Results (KER).
- Section 6: This section presents the metrics that would allow monitoring of progress to materialize the exploitation expectations.
- Section 7: The conclusion section summarizes the main findings and highlights the key takeaways from the document.
- Section 8: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document, providing a comprehensive list of the materials used to support the information presented.

2 6G Market Context and Needs

With the deployment of 5th Generation (5G) wireless networks worldwide in 2020, research on the 6th Generation (6G) wireless communications for the development of future mobile communication networks has been officially launched around the world.

5G networks were designed to provide enhanced Mobile BroadBand (eMBB), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) and ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (uRLLC) services. 6G networks will have to support the new application scenarios of the future (2030 and beyond) and their corresponding challenging performance requirements.

The preliminary studies on 6G [4][5] agree on that, in the 6G era, an air-space-ground integrated network communication system will be built to realize a ubiquitous network for full coverage and support a new range of challenging scenarios.

Figure 2-1 6G high level architectural layers, technologies, and applications [6]

However, diverse applications and communication scenarios, as depicted in Figure 2-1, ultra-heterogeneous network connections, and service requirements for extreme performance mean higher requirements on the bandwidth, latency, security, connection density, and flexibility of 6G networks. The increase in scale, density, diversity, and complexity in 6G networks will bring several significant new challenges.

One of them is how to manage an enormous number of resources (including spectrum, computation, storage, energy as well as devices and infrastructures) and encourage large-scale resource sharing for higher efficiency.

The 6G networking will also face several security issues (e.g., access control, data exchange, privacy protection, certification, etc.) even much more demanding and challenging than in 5G, given the augmented heterogeneity and density of 6G networks. Such security issues will, in turn, aggravate the separation between networks, subnetworks and their hosts, making efficient resource sharing even harder. This goal is impeded by several trust-related issues that are often neglected in network designs.

On the other hand, in the foreseeable future, we may expect many micro-Mobile Network Operators (MNO) to appear with flexible business models that are responsive to specific market demands (i.e., verticals). Such a micro-MNO paradigm will require real-time

decentralized spectrum allocation and fine-grained resource utilization across time and space. Therefore, there is a need for a trustable and scalable solution that can enable quasi-real-time spectrum and infrastructure sharing among hundreds of MNOs as well as improving Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and financial interaction between MNOs and end users.

In this regard, it is essential for MNOs to change their existing centralized business strategy for a more flexible decentralized architecture led by Software Defined Networking (SDN), Network Function Virtualization (NFV), and intelligent management.

The telecom sector continues its transition towards the virtualization of the infrastructure, from the standard purchase of Network Services (NS) packaged in a service-specific hardware to a model based on the acquisition of the software of the NS and then its delivery in a general-purpose virtualized hardware. As a result, the digitalization of assets and their commercialization in a marketplace will play a central role in 6G networks.

Distributed Ledger Technologies, and in particular its more extended type Blockchain, is an innovative and revolutionary technology that presents a promising solution to solve the trust problems in current 5G and future 6G wireless networks. Building on its nature of decentralization, transparency, anonymity, immutability, traceability, and resiliency, blockchain can establish cooperative trust among separate network entities and facilitate quite a few functionalities for wireless networks (i.e., efficient resource sharing, trusted data interaction, secure access control, privacy protection, and tracing, certification, and supervision).

In parallel, the different terms and conditions of future applications will need to be guaranteed in complex 6G networks. **Blockchain-enabled Smart Contracts (SC)**, which allow execute contracts in an automated way without manual and third-party intervention, can be a good solution, as they may help to increase efficiency by cutting down administration processes and time and saving services cost, while reduce the risk of errors and disputes.

Together, SCs and Blockchain provide a powerful combination that can enable the creation of a digital, decentralized marketplace that is agile, transparent, secure, and efficient, enabling greater innovation and collaboration. By leveraging these technologies, stakeholders in the telco industry and, even new players, can transact with each other more effectively the commercialization of virtualized services, infrastructure, and networks. Blockchain and SCs contracts are poised to play significant roles in shaping the future of 6G networks by enhancing security, enabling novel services, and transforming network management.

Furthermore, the advent of 6G networks necessitates robust mechanisms for efficient resource discovery and management, as well as adherence to predefined service standards. The **Smart Discovery** system within the 6GENABLERS framework addresses the challenge of managing diverse resources by leveraging intelligent algorithms to facilitate dynamic and context-aware resource discovery. This capability enables stakeholders to efficiently explore and engage with the plethora of resources available in the marketplace, contributing to its agility and effectiveness.

Additionally, the **SLA Assurance** system is crucial for ensuring that interactions within the marketplace meet predefined service standards. By automating the verification of compliance with SLAs in real-time and monitoring participant performance against

agreed-upon benchmarks, this system enhances trust among participants and fosters transparent and accountable collaborations within the marketplace. Together, these components augment the functionality and reliability of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, positioning it as a key player in the evolution of 6G networks.

2.1 Introduction to Technology Pillars

2.1.1 DLT and Smart Contracts

Blockchain technology is a good solution for distributed trading and smart contracts. This technology makes it possible to exchange digital items without having an intermediary validating the transaction. The blockchain ensures all elements and participants of a transaction are valid, enforcing the rules. Blockchain technology and distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) are developing rapidly. They have been extremely successful in the field of finance, authenticating transactions as it paves the way for a high level of transparency and security.

A complete blockchain incorporates several crucial features. First, distributed design enables participants connected on nodes updating independently when new transactions occur. Encryption using public and private keys records data securely and semi-anonymously by means of wallets, providing an address granting pseudonymity. Immutability by means of signed, time-stamped and sequential records which can't be changed unless all participants agree to do so. Decentralization ships consensus rules approving transactions.

SCs were first introduced by N. Szabo in 1997 [7]. The first and most famous SC is Ethereum, which is a remarkable solution for many applications.

SCs are mainly digital programs where contract clauses are written with programmable codes that can be programmed to automatically execute specific actions when predetermined conditions are met. For instance, a SC could be encoded to automatically transfer funds from one account to another when a specific date is reached or when a particular event occurs (i.e., a product being delivered, or a service being completed). By automating contract execution in this way, SCs can reduce the need for manual intervention, increasing efficiency and reducing the risk of errors and disputes. SCs can automate a wide range of business processes, such as insurance claims processing, real estate transactions, and even voting systems.

2.1.2 Smart Contracts vs. Traditional Contracts

Traditional contracts are based on manual, time-consuming processes that involve intermediaries (e.g., lawyers and brokers), as they need to be completed by a trusted third party in a centralized manner and, consequently, resulting in long execution time and extra cost. In contrast to conventional transactions, with SCs, the whole process is done in a peer-to-peer manner without the intervention of third parties. As a result, the turnaround time and transactional cost can be greatly saved. SCs have the following advantages compared with conventional contracts:

- **Reducing risks.** Due to the immutability of blockchains, SCs cannot be arbitrarily altered once they are issued. Moreover, all the transactions that are stored and duplicated throughout the whole distributed blockchain system are traceable and

auditable. As a result, malicious behaviors like financial fraud can be greatly mitigated.

- **Cutting down administration and service costs.** Blockchain assures the trust of the whole system by distributed consensus mechanisms without going through a central broker or a mediator. SCs stored in blockchains can be automatically triggered in a decentralized way. Consequently, the administration and services costs due to the intervention from the third party can be significantly saved.
- **Improving the efficiency of business processes.** The elimination of the dependence on an intermediary can significantly improve the efficiency of the business process. Take the supply-chain procedure as an example. The financial settlement will be automatically completed in a peer-to-peer manner once the predefined condition is met (e.g., the buyer confirms the reception of the products). As a result, the turnaround time can be significantly reduced.

Table 2-1 compares the traditional contracts with SCs:

Table 2-1 Comparison between SC and traditional contract [7]

Requirements	Smart Contract	Traditional contract
Third-party	Not required	Banks, Regulators
Execution time	minutes	days
Transparency	available	Not available
Signature	Digital	Manual
Process	Automatic	manual
Achieve	easy	hard
Security	Highly secure	limited

2.1.3 Blockchain Platforms Supporting Smart Contracts

SCs can be developed and deployed in different **blockchain platforms**, each of them with distinctive features for developing SCs, including contract programming languages, contract code execution, and security levels. [8] enumerates some of the platforms that support high-level programming languages to develop SCs:

- **NXT** is an open-source blockchain platform that relies entirely on a proof-of-stake consensus protocol. It includes a selection of SCs that are currently living. However, it is not turing-complete, meaning that only the existing templates can be used, and no personalized SC can be deployed.
- **Ethereum** is the first blockchain platform for developing SCs. It supports advanced and customized SCs with the help of a turing-complete Virtual Machine (VM), called the Ethereum VM (EVM). EVM is the runtime environment for SCs, and every node in the Ethereum network runs an EVM implementation and executes the same instructions. Solidity, as a high-level programming language, is used to write SCs, and the contract code is compiled down to EVM bytecode and deployed on the blockchain for execution. Ethereum is currently the most popular development platform for SCs and can be used to design various kinds of decentralized applications in several domains.
- **Hyperledger Fabric** is an open-source enterprise-grade distributed ledger technology platform proposed by IBM that supports SCs. It offers modularity and versatility for a broad set of industry use cases. The modular architecture for Hyperledger Fabric accommodates the diversity of enterprise use cases through plug and play components. It is permissioned, so several business-related

organizations can join in through a membership service provider. Its network is built up from the peers whose are owned and contributed by those organizations.

Ethereum and Hyperledger Fabric SCs differ in multiple aspects. While Solidity is the well-known programming language used to write Ethereum SCs, Hyperledger Fabric supports multi-language SCs, such as Go, Java, and Javascript. For contract code execution, the contract code in Ethereum is included in a transaction, which is propagated in the peer-to-peer network, and any miner that receives this transaction can execute it in its local VM. In Hyperledger Fabric, when a transaction is created by the application, the transaction is only executed and signed by specified peers (endorsing peers). After receiving the application’s transaction proposal, each of these endorsing peers independently executes it by invoking the chain-code to which the transaction refers. For security, the chain code runs within a container environment (e.g., Docker) for isolation.

6GENABLERS-DLT project uses **Hyperledger Fabric**. Hyperledger [9] is an open-source joint effort to advance in blockchain technology. By embracing the open-source principles established by the Linux Foundation, Hyperledger Foundation promotes interoperability and standardization, paving the way for the widespread adoption of secure and scalable blockchain and digital trust solutions across industries and sectors. Figure 2-2 depicts the different frameworks and tools hosted by the Hyperledger Foundation and Figure 2-3 illustrates their timeline.

Figure 2-2 Frameworks and tools hosted by Hyperledger [10]

Figure 2-3 Hyperledger Foundation Timeline [10]

2.1.4 Smart Contracts Languages

A SC language is a programming language used to create self-executing contracts that automatically enforce agreement terms.

Different blockchains platforms support different languages, which means that there's no one-language-fits-all solution for smart contract developers.

Table 2-2 shows other popular SC languages as well as the blockchain platforms that support them.

Table 2-2 Smart Contract languages and blockchain platforms [11]

LANGUAGE	COMPATIBLE BLOCKCHAINS	MOST SIMILAR TO...
Solidity	Arbitrum, Avalanche C-Chain, BNB Chain, Ethereum, Harmony, Hedera Hashgraph, Klaytn, Metis, Moonbeam, Moonriver, Optimism, Polygon, Tron	JavaScript
Vyper	Same as Solidity	Python
Yul	Same as Solidity	Solidity
Cairo	StarkNet/StarkEx	Python
Rust	Solana, Polkadot, Cosmos	C, C++
Move	Aptos, Sui	Rust

2.1.5 Smart Discovery and SLA Assurance

In the landscape of modern telecommunications, service-level agreements (SLAs) play a pivotal role in delineating expectations between service providers and customers. An SLA outlines the products or services to be delivered, designates a single point of contact for end-user issues, and establishes metrics for monitoring and approving the effectiveness of processes.

As the telecommunications industry evolves to meet the demands of 6G networks, service and network assurance modernization become increasingly imperative. This modernization is vital for achieving various service and infrastructure objectives, including but not limited to automated operations, enhanced customer experiences, intent-driven orchestration, and the delivery of high-quality services.

In response to these evolving needs, solutions and near-term product roadmaps have emerged, focusing on integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

technologies. These advancements enable the correlation of service and network parameters, thereby supporting proactive service assurance and facilitating robust SLA support. Through AI/ML-driven analytics, telecom operators can anticipate and address potential service disruptions before they impact end-users, thereby enhancing overall network reliability and customer satisfaction.

Alongside advancements in service and network assurance, the capability to effectively navigate over the set of available offers to find the most suitable ones is of paramount importance. The decentralization and high population of the Marketplace, however, present challenges in finding the right offer. To address this complexity, a discovery service is implemented to facilitate interactions between consumers and the offering platform.

By leveraging intelligent algorithms, such smart discovery service empowers stakeholders to efficiently explore and engage with the diverse resources available in the Marketplace. This service aims to return a customized subset of offers that best satisfy the consumer's expectations. Utilizing smart selection techniques based on ML, the discovery service enables programmatic and intent-based discovery, reducing the burden on consumers and allowing them to focus on core business objectives.

Through contextual understanding and dynamic resource discovery, the Smart Discovery system enhances the agility and effectiveness of the telecommunications ecosystem. It enables telecom operators to swiftly identify and deploy resources tailored to specific needs and preferences, thereby optimizing network performance, and facilitating seamless service delivery. As telecommunications networks continue to expand in complexity and scale, the Smart Discovery system serves as a cornerstone for navigating the evolving landscape and unlocking new opportunities for innovation and collaboration.

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace facilitates the availability of network resources, empowering operators, resource and service providers to seamlessly discover and access the resources necessary to fulfill contractual obligations. This streamlined collaboration process is a significant advancement in 6G networking, as it provides a unified platform for resource sharing and collaboration while aligning with the sustainability vision of 6G.

2.2 State of the Art

2.2.1 Distributed Ledger Technologies

Blockchain-inspired solutions often aim to reengineer existing manual processes specific to an individual organization or industry. Because blockchain-inspired solutions are developed for use inside an enterprise or between known parties, they are by definition centralized in design. Their owners describe them as closed, private, permissioned, enterprise and proprietary.

Nowadays, the most prominent commercial use of blockchain and DLT technologies is related to cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin or Ethereum. In a nutshell, all existing blockchain platforms can be summarized into the following main types: (i) permissioned (e.g., private or consortium), (ii) permissionless (e.g., public) and (iii) hybrid. In general, a permissioned network is a private blockchain network with only authorized members

(one member or group of members), whereas a permissionless network is a public blockchain network setup intended to allow public participation.

Hyperledger Fabric is an open source blockchain [11], created by IBM and further developed by the Hyperledger Foundation. Instead of such constrained domain-specific languages, it can offer the use of smart contracts (also known as chain code) to express logic with general-purpose scripting languages like Go, Java, and Node.js. Hyperledger Fabric supports pluggable consensus algorithms (e.g., PBFT, Raft, and Kafka), allowing one to choose the consensus protocol that best suits their needs. Hyperledger Fabric is considered one of the best option due to its privacy, scalability, and performance features. It also offers privacy for communication via the design of channels, private data control via the access control list, and membership mechanism to restrict channel access. Thus, Hyperledger Fabric enables one to configure privacy via channels and private data access, which is a very important functionality. Quorum [13] and Multichain [14] use private transactions to hide the transaction data so that limited users can access them.

However, these systems weren't designed to handle the complexity, size and scale of the machine-to-machine transactions made possible by digital platforms.

Furthermore, the interoperability fosters blockchain scalability by enabling transactions to be offloaded to other blockchains. It is also considered as a crucial requirement for the survivability and manageability of blockchain systems. However, current blockchains are not intrinsically designed to be interoperable, while each blockchain is focused on resolving specific challenges within industries in a siloed manner. In a nutshell, a transaction is based on smart contracts, hence in different blockchain infrastructures, different data structures are used. Thus, to transfer data structure from one blockchain to another, a conversion is needed.

Smart Contracts are often used to automate the execution of an agreement so that all parties can be certain of the outcome immediately, without the need for an intermediary. They can also automate a workflow such that when circumstances are met, the next action is executed. In general, a smart contract is a contract that is written in code and intended to execute a set of instructions. In essence, smart contracts operate according to the "if/when...then" pattern and are written into code on a blockchain. However, a smart contract embodies domain-specific logic, which may come from legal documents, user agreements, or other business process requirements. Furthermore, transactions with the appropriate payload data can call the APIs directly.

Additionally, in any blockchain platform, one should handle how to reach an agreement among a quorum of blockchain nodes. Since there is no centralized node in the blockchain network, it is challenging to reach consensus.

Another key challenge is searching over blockchain. It is a difficult task as the application of queries to the blockchain is complex.

Moreover, the reputation represents collective information about the trustworthiness of users and retailers in the online marketplace. When feedback ratings are not possible, an equal reputation is assigned in the aggregation mechanism based on secure multi-party computation, private secret sharing, and discrete log commitment. Thus, trustworthiness of data stored in the blockchain ledger is prevalent ignoring data provenance.

In some blockchain scenarios, smart contracts would need to receive data from outside the DLT network. However, the isolation of blockchain networks from the outside blocks to obtain data from outside sources by themselves. To overcome this limitation, oracles are external data agents that collect real-world data and insert them into the blockchain as transactions so that smart contracts can utilize them.

Another challenge focuses on the access control mechanism, which grants entrance to data through the application of policies. Hyperledger Fabric has an inherent access control mechanism, called membership service provider (MSP). MSP is a component that offers an abstraction of membership operations such as cryptographic mechanisms and protocols behind issuing certificates, validating certificates, and user authentication.

Finally, the lack of mechanisms for key management and recovery intricates the accountability and identity as blockchain protocols know only about private keys (random numbers) and do not link any natural identity to accounts. This has been an intentional part of the pseudo-anonymous design of blockchains. However, this lack of real-world identity causes the complete loss of accountability of humans and organizations. Key management is yet one of the unsolved problems on the internet and especially on decentralized solutions. Conventional backup and recovery mechanisms for keys are the physical backup, the cloud services for password management and the social recovery. While, for identity management when using identity providers (IdPs), responsible for identity attestation, management and use, the provider owns of the user identity. As an alternative, Decentralized identifiers (DIDs) enable users to keep identity ownership. Blockchain can store DIDs and documents which contain the public key for the entity and other public information the identity owner wishes to reveal to others.

2.2.2 Smart Contracts

In [8], a thorough analysis about the latest studies on SCs is performed. It categorizes the SC research in two big blocks: the first one groups those studies related to how improve SCs by addressing their challenges, such as functionality, verification, performance, vulnerabilities, and lack of trustworthy data feeding; the second one focuses on those studies that address domain-specific challenges while using SCs.

Smart contract improvement

- **Programing centric solutions:** SCs are basically pieces of software code that can be executed automatically, so programming SCs correctly is an important research direction. In this sense, new programming languages have been developed and studied to address existing domain-specific language vulnerabilities.
- **Formal verification-centric solutions:** Formal testing can ensure that a smart contract behaves and performs as expected, but it can't help developers to find bugs or vulnerabilities. Formal analysis and verification of SCs before deployment on the blockchain can help to avoid security vulnerabilities. Since existing programming languages, such as Solidity, are not built for formal verification, several researchers have proposed alternative approaches to improve the SC functionality verification. Although formal verification tools have been widely adopted by several researchers, this research direction still deserves a lot of attention.
- **Performance optimization-centric solutions:** Some performance issues in blockchain systems are, for example, throughput bottleneck, limited scalability, transactions latency. To overcome performance issues in SC systems, some

researchers have proposed solutions for performance optimization, like executing SCs in parallel instead of sequentially. However, this faces the challenge of how to execute contracts that depend on each other at the same time.

- **Security optimization-centric solutions:** Security of a SC refers to its robustness against attacks from malicious users that exploit generally the contract security vulnerabilities or the lack of trustworthy data feeding to inject malicious data. Discovering potential vulnerabilities in the execution of contracts is important to improve the security and credibility of contracts. On the other hand, the SC execution requires some external data about real-world states and events from outside the blockchain. Therefore, trustworthy data feeding mechanisms (known as Oracles) are required to build a bridge between blockchain and the external world (e.g., Web API). Thus, Oracles retain an enormous amount of power over SCs because the data they provide determines how the SCs execute.

Optimizing SC codes can effectively reduce potential vulnerabilities and ensure efficient and secure execution of contracts. However, the existing studies are still immature, and unknown vulnerabilities or bugs cannot be detected to be replaced. Thus, the optimization of SCs needs further research.

Smart contract usage

- **Data management-centric solutions:** Blockchain-based data management emerged as a platform to facilitate transparent data transactions between untrustworthy involved parties on the network. Three potential areas of application of SCs are suggested:
 - **Data Provenance:** As blockchain can offer an immutable storage of records, SCs can be used for verifying the data origins before storing them. Ensuring data provenance can increase data transparency and enforce data integrity.
 - **Data Access:** SCs can be used to transform the access control policies evaluation process into a distributed smart contract execution.
 - **Data Sharing:** Blockchain technology can ensure efficient and secure data sharing in a peer-to-peer network, as offers immutable storage of records that improves data handling transparency and can host SCs to authenticate users and verify authorizations.
- **Device management-centric solutions:** One of the technical challenges of having billions of devices deployed worldwide is the ability to manage and synchronize them. Using the current model of the server-client system may have some limitations for device management thus, several researchers are studying the benefits of blockchain use in this field. Specifically, SCs are chosen to guarantee authentication, synchronization, and data integrity while running on top of a decentralized and transparent network.
- **Cloud-related solutions:** In cloud computing, both customers and service providers agree on a set of requirements, obligations, and rights that are valid during the contract lifetime. Blockchain-enabled SCs enable changes in the agreement terms at runtime through the definition of conditions and actions.
- **Cross-organizational collaboration-driven usage solutions:** SCs help to record an agreement between several untrustworthy parties in the form of code that cannot be altered or changed once deployed on the blockchain. Thus, SC

development allows substituting traditional contracts and develops business growth in several industries. Cross-organizational collaboration-driven smart contract usage solutions are categorized into:

- **Profit-centric solutions:** Profit-centric solutions aim at increasing the profit by reducing real-time tracking costs, improving cross-border payments, and enhancing distributed problem-solving transparency. The smart contract protocol aims to make contracts more secure, executed in real-time, and more transparent, which are the exact challenges with the existing profit-centric cross-organizational collaboration. Examples of profit-centric solutions:
 - **Tracking-based solutions:** SCs can be used to automate the transfer of various types of ownership of assets, property, and value and therefore lead to more visible and less-intermediated working processes.
 - **Digital asset-based solutions:** Because of their resilience to tampering, SCs are appealing in many scenarios, especially in those which require transfers of money to respect certain agreed rules, like in financial services. The lack of a centralized authority reduces costs and provides more control and access to the investors.
 - **Crowdsourcing-related solutions:** Blockchain is considered as a promising technology that aims at addressing the main challenges of this kind of solutions (i.e., cost, vulnerability to malicious attacks) by eliminating the single point of failure, enhancing transparency, and enforcing rules using SCs.
- **Non-profit-centric solutions:** Blockchain technology is needed in a cross-organizational collaboration area suffering from a decline in trust from involved parties (e.g., volunteers, donors, voters, etc.) who are unable to know how their contributions are spent/handled. Indeed, SCs enable “fully auditable” performance data, which is secure and extremely difficult to falsify or hack.

Although SCs fulfill many conditions related to data/device management, they have some drawbacks based on basic design principles of blockchain technology. First, the data stored on SCs are publicly readable through public transactions with no read access restrictions. Thus, it is required to avoid storing private or device keys on SCs. For solving transparency problems related to blockchain, future research might investigate deploying complex cryptographic solutions for securing data stored on SCs without boosting cost. Second, the cost of storing data on the blockchain is very high. Therefore, creating hybrid solutions is required to benefit from the traceability of data transactions that are offered by blockchain networks, and the efficient and private access and storage of data provided by external data repositories.

2.2.3 Potential Risks of Smart Contracts

Although SCs are a promising solution with great potential to reshape and foster innovation in many conventional business procedures, they still present a few challenges to be solved.

Security issues:

The decentralized power of blockchain may be at risk of abuse especially due to SCs and consensus mechanisms in blockchain technology are vulnerable to malicious network attacks or tampering. Like common distributed systems, blockchain, and, therefore, SCs, inevitably may suffer from various security attacks [4]. Some examples are:

- **Alternative history attack:** Also called a blockchain reorganization attack as it is a high-severity attack that manipulates the blockchain reorganization mechanism.
- **Selfish mining:** It happens when the attacker forks the chain and mines blocks without broadcasting to the main chain. Upon broadcasting, their fork can hijack the main chain.
- **Cryptanalytic attack:** Aiming to break the cryptographic algorithm and expose its keys.
- **Nothing at stake:** In a nothing-at-stake attack, a validator creates multiple blocks to spend tokens multiple times. Because of the low cost of creating blocks in Point-of-Sale systems, there is no financial incentive to the network not to approve all the transactions, causing consensus to break down.
- **Traditional cyber-attack:** Traditional cyber-attacks, such as the ones listed below, still exist in blockchain:
 - **Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack**, which occurs when multiple blockchain nodes are flooded with invalid requests and their normal operations may be abruptly interrupted.
 - **Replay attack**, which intercepts the data packets of communicating parties and relay them to their destinations without modification.
 - **Man-in-the-middle attack**, in which attackers can intercept those data packages and inject new contents.
 - **Sybil attack**, where a plural of faulty information is injected into the network.
 - **Eclipse attack**, that, unlike Sybil attacks aiming at the entire blockchain network, the eclipse attack only cheats on one network target and forges a false view of blockchains.

Additionally, it is challenging to ensure the correctness of SCs due to vulnerabilities of computer programs to the faults and failures.

Legal, regulatory and compliance issues:

These issues are another crucial aspect of SC challenges. Some legal issues that can be cited are that, for example, each country has its own laws and regulations; hence, it is complicated to ensure compliance with all regulations. In addition, law clauses and conditions are not quantifiable, thus it is complicated to model these conditions in SCs so that they are appropriate.

Regulatory compliance also plays an important role in the SCs market, as SCs can be used to execute legally binding agreements and transactions. SCs must comply with relevant laws and regulations to be legally enforceable. SCs often involve the collection and processing of personal data, which may be subject to data protection laws such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the EU or the California Consumer

Privacy Act (CCPA) in the US, which stipulate that citizens have a “right to be forgotten”. Smart contract developers must ensure that their contracts comply with these regulations and that appropriate data protection measures are in place.

Immutability issue:

The immutability feature is an important characteristic of SCs. Indeed, once a SC is deployed, the code cannot be changed by any party. However, the dark side of the immutability concept in SCs lies mainly in the fact that in the event of any errors made in the code, the immutability feature of a SC prevents it from being rectified. Similarly, if circumstances change (e.g., the parties have mutually agreed to change the parameters of their business deal, or if there is a change in law, etc.), no simple path to amend a SC is possible. Therefore, extensive, and possibly expensive, reviews of the SC performed by experts before its deployment in a blockchain are required to address the immutability issue. Moreover, any blockchain nodes can be hacked or misused to report erroneous data that will be logged on the blockchain in an immutable manner.

Scalability issue:

Scalability is the primary concern for many blockchain networks, as it leads to network congestion and increases fees for transactions, and the time required to confirm the transactions. To address the scalability issue, extensive research focusing on increasing the number of transactions per second by SC platforms is required in the future. A solution called Layer 2 has appeared to tackle the blockchain scalability problem. While Layer 1 is the term used to describe the underlying main blockchain architecture, Layer 2 is an overlaying network that lies on top of the underlying blockchain. Thanks to Layer 2, a great portion of the work that would be performed by Layer 1 (the “main chain”) can be moved to the second layer. This way the “main-chain” provides security, while the second layer protocols provides better solutions for the scalability issue by offering high throughput.

Consensus mechanism issue:

The consensus mechanism plays the leading role to maintain security, scalability, and decentralization in the blockchain networks at the same time. There are several existing consensus algorithms, including Proof of Work (PoW), Proof of Stake (PoS), etc. Although the PoW algorithm enables security in the blockchain, it wastes resources. Thus, many organizations switch from the PoW algorithm to new consensus mechanisms that promise lower fees for transactions as well as lower energy costs for the block production process. Therefore, future studies can use new consensus mechanisms, such as Proof of Activity (PoA) or delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS) in order to test them and eventually improve their quality.

Complexity issues:

Complexity of smart contract systems and lack of knowledge and understanding among potential users and stakeholders can limit adoption, as potential users may not understand the value proposition of SCs or may be hesitant to invest in a technology they do not fully understand.

Lack of skilled professionals:

There is also a shortage of skilled professionals with the expertise to develop and implement SCs. This talent shortage can limit the growth and adoption of SCs, as companies may struggle to find qualified developers and consultants to help them implement this technology.

2.2.4 Smart Contracts in 6G

SCs, although not the sole future of 6G network management, offer exciting possibilities for enhancing efficiency, transparency, and security in next-generation wireless networks:

- **Efficiency:** SCs automate processes, reducing manual intervention and improving resource utilization.
- **Transparency:** All network participants can verify transactions and resource allocations.
- **Security:** Tamper-proof records enhance security and trust.

Researchers have explored integrating SCs into mobile network infrastructure, but it should be noted that the research on the usage of blockchain in the 6G industry is in its infancy and more studies should be done in this context. As 6G networks evolve, SCs could play a crucial role in [7]:

- **Resource Management:** Network resource management is one of the most important parts of the 6G network. Massive connectivity of users and diverse applications with different requirements demand intelligent resource management. The role of blockchain and SCs is inevitable. Next, we provide some examples of the usage of SCs in this field:
 - **Spectrum sharing:** Spectrum is one of the most important resources in telecommunication as it is limited and, therefore, should be used efficiently. Sharing spectrum is a solution to make the best use of it. For this to happen, an open market where every part could share their spectrum is needed. In addition, current spectrum sharing is not automatic and regulators can't track the usage of spectrum and so unfair allocation may happen. SC may be the best solution in this market.
 - **Unlicensed spectrum sharing:** Efficient spectrum utilization can happen when both licensed spectrum owners and unlicensed spectrum operators cooperate. SCs can provide an automated solution for the coordination between MNOs to share the unlicensed spectrum under guaranteed terms and conditions.
 - **Access fairness:** One of the main advantages of blockchain in resource management is to record its information such as location-based data. With this history of data, access fairness can be achieved. With a smart contract, access can be given to users who have not reached the specific threshold.
- **Network Virtualization:** SDN and NFV are key pillars in 6G communication networks. Network virtualization leads the way for network slicing which can give end-to-end control of the network to service providers. Despite the technical challenges to deploy network slicing, there is some administrative discussion

among parties who do not trust each other. The SC is the best way for these parties to allow the deployment of network slicing.

- **6G Multi Operator Network:** 6G is conceived as a multi-operator network that needs a framework for quasi-real-time spectrum and infrastructure trading between MNOs. The key aspect of this framework is the tokenization of spectrum and infrastructure. It has four main participants: spectrum regulator, spectrum owner, infrastructure owner, and end-user. Employing SLAs based on SCs, users can easily switch to the network provider with better coverage, quality, or price.
- **Local Area Mobile Network:** The infrastructure of mobile networks is fully centralized nowadays, which makes its deployment and maintenance so complex and costly. However, with the expensive cost of spectrum licenses, local and small MNOs can't enter the market. SCs can provide a great opportunity to trade spectrum between local and small operators and nationwide operators. They can buy unused spectrum in special areas or times from nationwide operators in real-time with SCs.
- **Quality of Service (QoS) Monitoring:** The current SLA for QoS monitoring is not trustworthy enough and can't guarantee the required QoS parameters. Otherwise, if SLA and SCs are deployed based on blockchain technology through a SC, it can limit the disputes and provide accountability.
- **Computing Power & Data Storage Management:** Use cases in 6G will require a large amount of data and processing this data needs a huge amount of computing power. However, these kinds of applications discharge the storage of mobile devices so soon. Blockchain can be the solution to this problem where people can use others' computing power in exchange for money in a double auction model. This process can be automated through a SC.

2.2.5 Smart Discovery and SLA Assurance

Telecom operators and service providers face the challenge of optimizing the utilization of their resources, including spectrum, computation, storage, and infrastructure. Marketplace solutions represent a great opportunity to generate revenues from underutilized resources.

In such a decentralized Marketplace, stakeholders require a streamlined process for discovering and accessing resources. A Smart Discovery system facilitates seamless collaboration by providing an intuitive interface for exploring available offers, reducing the time and effort required to find suitable resources. Customers expect rapid and reliable access to telecom services. By enabling quick and tailored resource discovery, the Smart Discovery system enhances customer experience, ensuring that their specific needs are met promptly and efficiently.

With the rapid evolution of telecommunications technologies and services, operators need agile solutions that can adapt to changing market dynamics. A Smart Discovery system offers flexibility by enabling real-time updates and adjustments to resource offerings, allowing operators to respond promptly to shifting demands. Likewise, as telecommunications networks continue to grow in scale and complexity, operators require scalable solutions that can support increasing volumes of exposed resources.

Telecom operators seek to differentiate themselves through innovative service offerings. The Smart Discovery system fosters service innovation by providing insights into

emerging market trends and enabling the rapid deployment of new services based on consumer preferences and demand patterns.

In a competitive telecommunications market, operators that can effectively leverage their resources and innovate in service delivery gain a competitive edge. The Smart Discovery system provides operators with a strategic advantage by enabling them to differentiate their offerings, attract new customers, and retain existing ones through personalized and efficient resource discovery experiences.

The cloud market represents a rapidly developing market sector that combines IT functionality (e.g. computing, storage, and data management) with wide-area networking, delivered as a set of services. This market is mature in terms of both adoption and standardization, due to its rapid expansion. Thus, there are many services already available for procurement by governments covering: Software as a Service (SaaS); Platform as a Service (PaaS); and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS).

Within this market, the instrument used to govern the relationship between the end user (the Service Customer) and the service provider (the Service Provider) is the contract entered into between these two parties, referred to as Service Level Agreement (SLA). Given the global nature of offerings, SLAs usually span many jurisdictions which often have their own applicable legal requirements, in particular with respect to the performance of the service. The SLA definitions also need to consider different perspectives from technical specifications, economical clauses as it is intrinsically related to billing and cost, and governance regulations to establish the obligations and responsibilities.

To have a more accurate and granular specification the SLAs can identify a set of service level objectives (SLOs), as measurable characteristic of a cloud service for which the service provider makes a commitment. Some SLOs and metrics widely considered are related to availability, reliability, security, data protection or other key performance indicators (KPIs).

Some existing SLA standards and best practices to rely on are [15]:

- ISO/IEC 19086
- SMART SLA Model
- CSCC Practical Guide to Cloud SLAs
- C-SIG SLA Guidelines
- ETSI Cloud SLA template

Private 5G networks have become a popular choice of various vertical industries to build dedicated and secure wireless networks in industry environments to deploy their services with enhanced service flexibility and device connectivity to foster industry digitalization. Thanks to the virtualization of those infrastructures, SLA techniques coming from virtualized infrastructures and clouds can be adopted.

SLAs in non-public networks (NPNs) widely refers to KPIs where the solution often lies on orchestration of network slices [16], meaning the management of network slices lifecycle and the operation of the Communication Service Management Function (CSMF), Network Slice Management Function (NSMF) and Network Slice Subnet Management Function (NSSMF) defined by 3GPP. When the processing capacity is targeted, the management of virtualized containers in the Virtualized Infrastructure

Manager (VIM), and the Virtualized Network Functions Manager (VNFM), their scaling or migration to other locations come into play. Here, the query to the Operational Support System (OSS) to ask for resource availability of exposed resources and the request to allocate resources are basic steps for managing a changeable demand when combined with load balancers and monitoring tools.

Unfortunately, there is no standard mechanism which exists to verify and ensure that delivered services satisfy the signed SLA agreement in an automatic way. There is no guarantee in terms of quality.

3 Market Analysis

This section delves into a comprehensive analysis of the market landscape, focusing on the potential opportunities and key players within the telecommunications ecosystem. The analysis encompasses three main subsections: Identification of Market Potential, Market Players, and Customer Segments, with the aim to evaluate the viability and scope of the proposed solutions within the broader market context.

3.1 Identification of Market Potential

Blockchain establishes operations in cloud-based networks that build blockchain applications. Third-party services are a relatively recent development in the rapidly growing field of blockchain technology. Blockchain solutions provide access to cloud-based services for creating and hosting smart contracts. Blockchain solutions are being adopted by an increasing number of small, medium-sized, as well as big businesses to simplify their operations, while keeping security, high immutability, secure decentralization, and cost-effectiveness to perform quick and efficient transactions. Blockchain solutions enable trade in a broad range of assets. Here, the adoption of blockchain technology by the market will provide better tools to manage expensive and opaque processes.

According to [17], the global blockchain technology market size was valued at USD 17.46 billion in 2023 and is expected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 87.7% from 2023 to 2030, expecting to reach USD 1,431.54 billion.

This market growth is being driven by the increasing demand for secure and transparent transactions across many industries. Innovations such as cryptocurrency, tokenization of assets, blockchain-as-a-service, and the blend of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with blockchain are reshaping the market. These transformative trends are offering convenience, security, and accessibility, revolutionizing today’s financial landscape.

Figure 3-1 Blockchain Technology Market [17]

To apply this technology in different vertical sectors, EU-funded blockchain-related projects have received until 2023 347M€ to support blockchain-related research and innovation [18].

In any case, the solutions are far from being interoperable as the design of data structures is intrinsically related to the application sector meaning an implementation of the blockchain tailored to specific data models. An example of that is that Mackinsey report that a UK startup, Provenance, has raised US\$800,000 to adapt blockchain technology to trace food [19].

Blockchain as a Service (BaaS) is a blockchain service offering that allows customers to use cloud-based services to develop, use and host their blockchain apps, functions, and smart contracts.

Blockchain as a Service is expected to play a crucial role in IT in the coming years. It has started to emerge exponentially because more and more companies now understand the advantages of the blockchain. Blockchain-as-a-Service providers like IBM, Microsoft Azure and other big companies have discovered BaaS to make blockchain implementation simpler for organizations whose core competencies remain in fields other than IT. It helps organizations focus more on their core areas while not worrying about the development space. Azure portfolio includes support for Quorum, Corda, Hyperledger Fabric and Ethereum. AWS includes Hyperledger Fabric and Ethereum. Even SAP is now providing blockchain solutions with the SAP Cloud Platform Blockchain also called Leonardo.

The key claim for BaaS solutions is the cost. When it comes to analyzing the cost of self-hosted blockchain infrastructure, the total cost of ownership is expected to be high because of start-up costs (infrastructure, personnel, software, licensing, hardware, consulting and more), retirement costs (decommissioning of server racks) and operational costs (monitoring, cost per transactions, bandwidth expenses). Moreover, the cost of building and deploying a single smart contract under the former model is very expensive. A blockchain application hosted in the cloud as a part of the BaaS offering can be cheap per allocated CPU hour. It means users pay as they go. The actual costs in the BaaS model depend on factors like transaction rate, the maximum number of concurrent transactions, the payload size on transactions and so on. For example, Amazon AWS Managed Blockchain Service's Pricing depends on factors like peer nodes, data written to the network, network membership, data transfer and peer node storage [20].

According to a recent market study [21], the BaaS market is currently big and will continue growing in the next years as a cloud-based service where it is expected that Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) become a key actor for shaping the market with solutions for identity management, supply chain management, and payments integrated with BaaS systems while removing intermediaries and the lack of transparency. The study forecasts that SMEs are expected to dominate the blockchain-as-a-service market. Additionally, the study provides a picture of the presence of blockchain in different verticals such as Banking, Financial Services and Investment (BFSI), Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG), Healthcare, Manufacturing, Retail and e-commerce, Transportation and logistics, Media and utilities. According to Gartner [22], the technology could generate as much as \$3.1 trillion in new business value by 2030.

Regarding the global SCs market size, according to [23] it was valued at USD 684.3 million in 2022 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 82.2% from 2023 to 2030, to reach USD 73,773.0 million by 2030.

Among the key factors driving the market growth of SCs, we include:

- **Increasing adoption of blockchain technology.** Blockchain technology is becoming increasingly popular as businesses look for more secure, efficient, and transparent ways to manage data and execute transactions.
- **Advantages of SCs over traditional contracts.** For example, SCs are a critical component of the Decentralized Finance (DeFi) ecosystem, which has grown rapidly in recent years. As more people adopt DeFi, the demand for SCs is increasing.
- **COVID-19 pandemic.** The pandemic forced many businesses to operate remotely and led to a greater demand for contactless transactions as people seek to minimize physical contact. This provoked a significant increase in the adoption of digital technologies. SCs, that provide a secure and efficient way to automate business processes and reduce the need for manual intervention, are a natural fit for businesses seeking to operate remotely and are a clear example.

According to the 5G Observatory [15], despite the fragmentation of approaches between countries regarding spectrum for campus/private networks and its negative impact on economies of scale in the particularly strategic area of new industrial use cases, the interest in local spectrum licenses, which are sometimes known as campus licenses, has increased in recent months. These licenses are awarded on a localized basis and are typically used for 5G private networks by various industries.

Thus, one major current trend is the fact that private 5G networks (also known as non-public networks) are growing steadily, offering an alternative approach to business solutions offered by Mobile Network Operators (MNOs). The private 5G network is intended to support the multiple features and functions of 5G, beyond 5G and 6G. So, some vendors that support private 5G networks for verticals and enterprises include Athonet, Nokia and FreedomFi [15]. Traditional operators and vendors typically use their public mobile network infrastructure as the underlying infrastructure for building such private network offers. Thus, in this case, it may be difficult for the operator to serve specific enterprise locations using its existing infrastructure. For example, providing coverage to machinery/equipment or people inside large metal-based structures of buildings, or at large-scale port facilities or in very remote locations that may be at the edge or outside the public operators' coverage area.

As private networks start to be operated, and potentially shared and traded SLA assurance is a key aspect to rely on the provisioned Network as a Service (NaaS) or local/edge cloud. This approach fosters innovations and business from companies with shorter and agile time to market.

In this sense, according to McKinsey studies [24], Zero-touch, digital self-service becomes the preferred form of service. Here the customer onboarding involves subscription-style products, whose pricing and terms are simple and that can be purchased online. Wherever possible, after-sales service and inquiries (including complaints) use accessible digital diagnostics and self-assessment tools. Here SLA assurance mechanisms make the difference [25].

The continuous adoption, updates and enhancement of virtualized and cloud infrastructures will become a huge investment of companies in the future [26]. Essentially, three corners of the virtualized infrastructures, rejuvenate, innovate, and pioneer, will be strategic for the maximization of the benefits. Then, the IT cost efficiencies across application development, the IT maintenance, the advanced analytics, the Internet of Things (IoT), the automation and the early adoption of emerging technologies, such as blockchain, quantum computing, augmented and virtual reality inside these infrastructures will mean \$1 trillion in value by 2030.

The studies from Gartner are also positive, aligned with McKinsey but putting the focus on cloud management routines, from inventory, monitoring and classification, provisioning, and orchestration with resource optimization. So, according to Gartner [27], SLA monitoring and enhancements for efficiency or performance are key solutions in the market.

3.2 Market Players

North America dominated the blockchain technology market in 2022 and accounted for over 37.0% share of the global revenue. The reason is mainly its robust ecosystem of tech startups, established corporations, and leading research institutions, which constitutes a fertile ground for innovation development. In addition, North America is home to a variety of industries which recognize the potential of blockchain technology, from finance and healthcare to supply chain management and energy.

Figure 3-2 Global Blockchain Technology Market: Trend by region, 2023-2030 [17]

However, Asia Pacific is expected to grow at the highest CAGR over the forecast period as some governments (i.e., China, Japan, and India) are promoting the use of blockchain technology due to its benefits, such as the high transparency and increased efficiency that may provide to multiple industries.

Among the key Blockchain Technology Companies, we can cite:

- IBM Corporation

- Microsoft Corporation
- The Linux Foundation
- Blockchain Tech LTD
- Chain
- Circle Internet Financial, LLC
- Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited
- Digital Asset Holdings, LLC
- Global Arena Holding, Inc. (GAHC)
- Monax Labs
- Ripple

The competitive landscape of the market is highly fragmented. The key players are focused on strategies such as partnerships to strengthen their market position and enhance their product offerings to better cope with the changing needs of users and stay competitive. As a result, market players are investing more in research and development and collaborating with universities worldwide to support technical development, academic research, and innovation in blockchain technology.

On the other hand, blockchain technology market has very few substitutes (Directed Acyclic Graphs, distributed ledger, and hash graphs among others), which are still evolving and have not gained the popularity equivalent to the blockchain technology yet.

As happened with blockchain technology, North America dominated the SCs industry in 2022, accounting for a revenue share of more than 31.0%. The presence of prominent SCs providers, the early adoption of blockchain technology and the supportive ecosystem for startups make this area a promising market for SCs.

Figure 3-3 Global SCs Market: Trend by region during 2023-2030 [23]

Similarly, the Asia Pacific market is expected to emerge as the fastest growing one in the next few years. This market's growth can be attributed to the increasing adoption of blockchain technology in the region, due to the governments' investments in blockchain technology and its applications, including SCs, as they recognize the potential of SCs in various sectors, such as supply chain management, real estate, and e-commerce.

Some prominent players in the global SCs industry include:

- ScienceSoft USA Corporation
- Innowise Group
- iTechArt
- 4soft
- Algorand
- IBM
- TATA Consultancy Services Limited
- Chainlink
- ELEKS
- Waves Technologies

As in Blockchain, SCs companies are investing in strategic initiatives, such as mergers and acquisitions, partnerships, and product launches to offer innovative solutions to their customers and stay ahead of the competition. For example:

- Algorand, a technology company that provides a platform for advanced blockchain-based applications, announced in March 2022, a significant technical update that allows the creation of sophisticated decentralized Applications (dApp) within the Algorand ecosystem. This represents a significant achievement in cross-chain interoperability, as developers can now build complex dapps using smart contract-to-contract calling.
- Chainlink, a web3 services platform provider, launched in March 2023 the serverless and self-service Chainlink Functions platform for developers to connect their SCs and dApps to Web 2.0 API. This platform allows builders to run customizable computations on Web 2.0 APIs through its network.

The SCs industry is constantly evolving, and providers are adopting various trends to meet the growing demand for SC solutions. Some of the latest trends SC providers are adopting include platform interoperability, customizable SC templates, low-code or no-code SC, and integration with DeFi.

3.3 Customer Segments

Blockchain provides integrity and transparency in transactions, making it especially appealing to sectors such as finance, healthcare, and supply chain management. Therefore, businesses across these domains are increasingly integrating blockchain solutions in their operations.

The financial services segment dominated the market in 2022, accounting for more than 37.0% share of the global revenue. The main reason is the Blockchain technology's ability to provide secure and efficient transactions. This technology is expected to be widely adopted in this vertical owing to factors such as rising cryptocurrencies, high compatibility with the industry ecosystem, rapid transactions, Initial Coin Offerings, and reduced total cost of ownership.

Figure 3-4 Global Blockchain Technology Market in 2022 by end-use [17]

The healthcare segment followed, being the one expected to grow at the highest CAGR over the next years. Regulation for protecting consumer data is stricter every day, which is somehow forcing companies across the globe, healthcare market included, to make investments in enhancing data security, which is, in turn, increasing the adoption of blockchain technology. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic increased the demand for digitalization across the healthcare sector, which thereby created the need for blockchain technology across the sector.

If we focus on the applications, the payments segment dominated the market in 2022 and accounted for more than 44.0% share of the global revenue. Blockchain technology improves payment system efficiency, minimizes operating costs, and offers transparency as well as reduces the need for a middleman in payment processing, which has increased its use in this segment. However, the digital identity segment is foreseen to experience the highest CAGR growth in the next years, due to the rapid growth that this segment is experiencing because of its potential to address critical challenges in the digital age. As our lives become more digitized, the need for secure and portable digital identities is key. Blockchain technology is a unique tool for verifying and managing digital identities. This innovation is gaining great interest, especially in sectors where identity verification is crucial, such as finance, healthcare, and government.

Regarding the enterprises segment, the large enterprises one dominated the market in 2022 and accounted for more than 67.0% share of the global revenue. Large enterprises in sectors like insurance, financial services, healthcare, and supply chains, which have access to adequate capital and different assets to adopt new technologies introduced in the market, are increasingly making efforts to digitalize their offerings, which is creating a demand for blockchain technology among them. It is expected, however, that the Small & Medium Enterprise (SME) segment will increase the blockchain technology use in the near future, as it may help them reduce issues in many operating areas. For example, blockchain-based storage applications enable small businesses to store data safely and cost-effectively, which is driving the demand for blockchain among small businesses.

Regarding SCs, fintech companies, at the forefront of innovation in the financial industry, are playing a vital role in the development and growth of this market. SCs technology helps them to improve the efficiency, security, and transparency of financial transactions and, therefore, they are integrating this technology with their current financial systems, such as payment processors and banking systems. This integration can streamline financial processes and reduce the costs associated with manual intervention and intermediaries.

The Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance (BFSI) segment dominated the market in 2022 and accounted for a global revenue share of more than 37.0%. Due to its inherent characteristics (self-executing, tamper-resistant, and self-verifying), SCs are being used for peer-to-peer transactions, error-free insurance claim processing, transparent audits, and seamless “know your customer” processing. Traditional contracts require significant paperwork and meticulous record-keeping to ensure financial auditing, while SCs offer advanced bookkeeping solutions by being tied to the distributed incorruptible code of the blockchain network.

The retail segment is expected to grow significantly over the next few years, as SCs can help automate and streamline supply chain management, ensuring transparency, efficiency, and cost savings. Through SCs, all parties involved in the supply chain can access and verify information about products (origin, quality, movement, etc.), creating a transparent and tamper-proof record of the supply chain. This transparency can help reduce the risk of fraud, counterfeit products, and unethical practices while ensuring compliance with regulations and industry standards.

Figure 3-5 Global SCs Market in 2022 by end-use [23]

The large enterprise segment dominated the market in 2022 with revenue share of 67.0%, as they are the ones with resources to invest in this kind of technologies, blockchain and SCs, and to hire experts to develop and implement smart contract solutions and train their employees on how to use them. Additionally, they often operate in highly regulated industries, such as finance and healthcare, where compliance is critical, something that can be ensured with SCs by automating processes and reducing the risk of human error.

SCs can offer SMEs cost-effectiveness and improved efficiency by automating many of their processes, reducing the risk of errors, and speeding up transaction times, so the segment's growth is expected in the coming years.

In addition to aforementioned sectors, which are at the front-front of the adoption of Blockchain and SCs technologies, Table 3-1 outlines some other verticals where the 6GENABLERS Marketplace could be of interest.

Table 3-1 Value of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace when applied to verticals.

Vertical	Favorable scenario
Mission Critical	Trading connectivity tethering with drones acting as a repeater or a portable/mobile base station providing connectivity to local area systems from first responders. Monitoring the KPIs to trigger any alert or alarm and provide information on connectivity to the application to understand the reliability of communications. This enables pausing/resuming cooperative modes and switching to stand alone/safety mode when data sending or receiving is not reliable.
Entertainment	Trading edge production and content access to media covering sports/events. QoS-based decisions on rate-control or Level of Detail (LoD) systems for media streaming are essential in any media application, especially on mobility or multi-party experiences like holographic eXtended Reality (XR) communications.
Connected Vehicles	Trading car data to develop CCAM applications driven by data captured from vehicles. Monitor the coverage to get extended sensors from surrounding vehicles and systems to be aware of the extended perception reliability.
Industry4.0	Governance from different data pipelines of SCADA systems accessing production data and information for corporative and outsourced/service data systems. Monitor different KPIs required by different data flows in the production chain from SCADA or Data Space with a connector, then report any IoT incident or issue to be reported to maintenance and quality departments.
Energy consumers	Contracting the mix of energy sources (renewables, carbon, nuclear, etc.) in order to accommodate demand and to create the carbon footprint passport. Monitoring the production of energy from different sources and forecasting the capacity to deal with a demand.

4 Business Analysis

This section is devoted to analyzing the business potential of the technical results coming from the project. We start by explaining the methodology used to carry out such analysis to identify then the exploitable results and analyze later their potential applying some commonly used tools.

4.1 Methodology

In this section, the methodological approach along with the tools that are employed to perform the business analysis are presented. In concrete, the methodology used by the EU H2020 funded project Evolved-5G [28] is adopted, which considers a stepwise approach:

- The first step is setting the basis and defining the terminology that will be used in relation to the exploitable outcomes of the project, their category and type.
- Second, the project outcomes, with special focus on exploitable results developed as part of the project work, are identified, and analyzed. For such analysis, the template shown in Table 4-1 is used.

Table 4-1 Template for the analysis of the project exploitable outcomes.

Exploitable result's name			
Description	Outcome Type		Outcome Category
	Target TRL category		
End Customer			
Target Markets			
Innovations			
Product Competition			

- As a third step, a concise gap analysis of each exploitable outcome is executed. For this, we use the well-known **SWOT** (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) **analysis** [29], a strategic planning and management technique that evaluates an object (i.e., person, organization, project, business, etc.). The template, shown in Table 4-2, is used to identify the internal and external factors that may affect the performance and growth or viability and sustainability of the object under study.
 - **strengths**: characteristics of the business or project that give it an advantage over others,
 - **weaknesses**: characteristics that place the business or project at a disadvantage relative to others,
 - **opportunities**: elements in the environment that the business or project could exploit to its advantage.

- and **threats**: elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the business or project.

Table 4-2 Template for SWOT analysis of the project exploitable outcomes [30]

INTERNAL FACTORS

STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –

EXTERNAL FACTORS

OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –

- Finally, as the fourth step, the **Value Proposition Canvas** of each exploitable outcome is created. The Value Proposition Canvas [31][32] is a business model tool that helps you make sure that a company's product or service is positioned around customers' values and needs. The tool was created by Alexander Osterwalder, Yves Pigneur, and Alan Smith, same authors of the Business Model Canvas, aiming to map the value perceived by customers. The primary purpose is, therefore, to create a match between the product and market. For this to happen, the Value Proposition Canvas explores more deeply these two (out of the nine) blocks from the Business Model Canvas: Customer Segment and Value Proposition.

The Value Proposition is broken down into:

- **Products and services**: the list of products and services targeting the value proposition to a specific customer segment.
- **Pain relievers**: the ways in which these products and services will alleviate specific Customer Pains.
- **Gain creators**: the ways in which these products and services can create gains for the Customer.

The Customer Segment describes the target customer profile and relevant key information to understand the expected value to be provided by project results:

- **Customer Jobs**: the existing customer jobs and business processes executed by the prospective (corporate) users that are relevant to each product.
- **Pains**: the risks, obstacles, problems related to the existing way of performing the Customer Jobs.

- **Gains:** the outcome customers want to achieve or concrete benefits they are seeking from their Jobs.

Figure 4-1 Value Proposition Canvas [31]

Figure 4-2 Value Proposition Canvas template [32]

4.2 Types of Exploitable Outcome

Various types of partners may participate in a Research and Development (R&D) funded project, such as Universities and Research Centers and commercial companies, including SMEs. Depending on their expertise and areas of interest, the exploitation strategy and activities may vary:

- Universities and Research Centers usually focus their exploitation activities on promoting the research work performed.
- Commercial companies and SMEs' exploitation activities are mainly involved with the exploitation of commercially oriented products.

In the light of this diversity, we can summarize the major categories of exploitable outcomes and associated types, as graphically depicted in Figure 4-3 [33]:

Figure 4-3 Partner and Outcome Types [33]

Where:

- **Product development:** Includes the introduction of new products or new product features. This outcome category is related mostly to commercial companies and SMEs.
- **Business development:** Includes enhancement of existing processes/services and/or the creation of new ones. This outcome category is also related mostly to commercial companies and SMEs.
- **Standardization:** Any partner actively involved in standardization and/or regulatory activities can promote the results of the project to provide contributions to relevant standards bodies.
- **Research achievements:** Including publications, IPRs and prototypes. This outcome category can be produced by all partners.
- **Other Achievements:** Includes any activities or tools aimed at enhancing processes/services related to the introduction/deployment of the project results.
- **Start-Up companies:** Companies or ventures that are focused on a single product or service that is project's exploitable outcome and indirectly pursuit a product development outcome. They can be new established entities or spinouts from big companies or spin-offs from Universities and Research Centers.

Trying to fit the 6GENABLERS-DLT outcomes in the above classification, the outcome types can be listed as follows:

- **Demonstrators:** Demonstrations of one or more project results/products in the field or in lab environment; either as a service proposition or an end-to-end solution addressing specific end-user needs. Demonstrators are usually joint results of more than one partner and partner types.
- **Prototypes:** Stand-alone, modular products, which have been either developed or enhanced in the context of the project. Prototypes may be developed by commercial companies and SMEs or by academic or research initiatives with no direct commercialization capability.

- **Validation Activities:** Activities aiming at validating the functionalities of specific products; these can be considered as exploitation activities aiming at increasing the technology readiness level of the associated products.
- **Contributions to standardization and publications:** Indirectly exploitable results delivered to the industry through standardization and dissemination paths.
- **Other:** Such as studies, algorithms, techno-economic tools, knowledge transfer etc.

4.3 Analysis of Key Exploitable Results

Of all the project outcomes, we will consider as key exploitable results the different systems that compose the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, namely: DLT, Smart Contracts, Smart Discovery, and SLA Assurance. In the sections below, we thoroughly analyze their business potential following the methodology and tools described at the beginning of this section.

4.3.1 Distributed Ledger Technologies

Table 4-3 lists the different results and knowledge relevant for other services and applications, which could be exploited in other industries and domains from the DLT system, resulting from the Vicomtech participation into the 6GENABLERS-DLT project.

Table 4-3 Analysis of KER outcomes from the DLT system

DLT system			
Description	Foundational element of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, ensuring transparency, security, and decentralization of record-keeping. It provides:		
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) KER_DLT_1: DLT technology. Used as a secure distributed database. 2) KER_DLT_2: DLT benchmark. Tests for automated benchmarking of DLT technologies. 3) KER_DLT_3: DLT chaincodes. Chaincodes for custom data structure. 4) KER_DLT_4: Open APIs. Design and development of Open APIs. 5) KER_DLT_5: Containerization. Automated deployment of multiple systems from different instances in different infrastructures. 6) KER_DLT_6: DID technology. Provisioning of DIDs as Primary Keys (PK) and Foreign Keys (FK). 		
	Outcome Type	Validation Activities (Knowledge, SW asset)	Outcome Category
	Target TRL category	4 – technology validated in lab.	
End Customer	Marketplace operator, who, for the sake of simplicity, in 6GENABLERS-DLT, we consider is the Communication Service Provider (CSP).		
Target Markets	All 6G verticals.		
Innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear features and limitations to satisfy Application and Service requirements. • Perform synthetic tests to appropriately size the infrastructure and demand to identify any bottleneck. • Adapt a development to a specific data model and apply modifications or updates during the implementation and integration phase. • Design, development, testing and protection of Open APIs including the integration of programmed autonomy. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Push developments to clouds from on premise virtualized infrastructures to vendors including automated configuration. • Map recording of trading transactions with service specific logic.
Product Competition	Other DLT implementations may be considered as competitors, but there is not a reference DLT-backed product for telco offers trading that we are aware of.

4.3.2 Smart Contracts

Table 4-4 identifies the project outcomes resulting from the SC system, which play a vital role in boosting the innovation process and enhancing the portfolio of products and technologies offered to customers within an organization like ATOS.

Table 4-4 Analysis of KER outcomes from the SC system

SC System			
Description	Key element for the creation of a trusted marketplace for xNF and service providers to engage in negotiations that are backed up by a SC. It allows:		
	1) offer resources and services, 2) visualize others´ offers, 3) place orders for them, 4) request their deployment.		
	Outcome Type	Prototype	Outcome Category
	Target TRL category	4 – technology validated in lab.	
End Customer	Marketplace operator, who, for the sake of simplicity, in 6GENABLERS-DLT, we consider is the CSP.		
Target Markets	All 6G verticals.		
Innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SC applied to 6G Networks. • Enables the creation of a trusted Marketplace Platform for the transaction of xNFs. 		
Product Competition	SCs for network services are not the specific offering of any product we are aware of.		

4.3.3 Smart Discovery

Table 4-5 showcases the project outcomes attributable to the Smart Discovery system, pivotal in advancing the innovation trajectory and enriching the array of technologies resulting from the i2CAT participation into the 6GENABLERS-DLT project.

Table 4-5 Analysis of KER outcomes from the SD system

SD system	
Description	This system empowers participants to efficiently explore and engage with resources available in the Marketplace. Through intelligent and intent-based algorithms, stakeholders can identify relevant resources based on specific needs and preferences. It provides: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Customized resource recommendations.

	2) Dynamic resource discovery. 3) Intent recognition and matching. 4) User-friendly offers exploration.			
	Outcome Type	Validation Activities (Knowledge, SW asset)	Outcome Category	Research achievements
	Target TRL category	4 – technology validated in lab.		
End Customer	Marketplace operator, who, for the sake of simplicity, in 6GENABLERS-DLT, we consider is the CSP.			
Target Markets	All 6G verticals.			
Innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralized resource access: Utilizing a decentralized marketplace model, enabling access to a wide array of resources from multiple providers. Machine Learning integration: Harnessing ML algorithms for intelligent and personalized resource recommendations, enhancing user experience. Intent-Based discovery: Introducing intent-based algorithms to match user needs with available resources, improving efficiency and relevance. Transparent and trustworthy: Leveraging blockchain technology for transparent and tamper-resistant record-keeping, fostering trust among participants. 			
Product Competition	Intent-based and ML-assisted discovery mechanisms for DLT-anchored Telco Marketplaces are not the specific offering of any product we are aware of.			

4.3.4 SLA Assurance

Table 4-6 lists the different results and knowledge relevant for other services and applications, which could be exploited in other industries and domains from the SLA Assurance system, resulting from the Vicomtech participation into the 6GENABLERS-DLT project.

Table 4-6 Analysis of KER outcomes from the SLA Assurance system

SLA Assurance system				
Description	The SLA assurance system automates the verification of compliance with predefined service standards, fostering trust and accountability among participants. It provides:			
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> KER_SLA_1: SLA policies. Definition of rules for metrics. KER_SLA_2: NaaS API. Abstraction of network assets and operation. KER_SLA_3: Network metrics. Metrics for different data structures and data lakes. KER_SLA_4: IoT messaging. IoT data bus to share information across systems (Zero Touch). KER_SLA_5: Containerization. Automated deployment of multiple systems from different instances in different infrastructures. KER_SLA_6: ML for time series. Prediction of time series in real time for network KPIs. 			
	Outcome Type	Validation Activities (Knowledge, SW asset)	Outcome Category	Research achievements
	Target TRL category	4 – technology validated in lab.		

End Customer	Marketplace operator, who, for the sake of simplicity, in 6GENABLERS-DLT, we consider is the CSP.
Target Markets	All 6G verticals.
Innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear features and limitations to satisfy Application and Service requirements. • Perform synthetic tests to appropriately operate an underlying infrastructure. • Adapt a development to a specific data model and identify target metrics during the implementation and integration phase. • Design, development, testing of IoT messaging including the integration of other systems using information. • Push developments to clouds from on premise virtualized infrastructures to vendors including automated configuration. • Train algorithms to identify demand and any bottleneck in real time.
Product Competition	SLA management platforms with violation detection & prediction capabilities.

4.4 SWOT Analysis

4.4.1 Distributed Ledger Technologies

The SWOT chart of the DLT exploitable assets is depicted in Table 4-7.

Table 4-7 SWOT chart of the DLT system outcomes

INTERNAL FACTORS

STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brings all blockchain benefits such as transparency, immutability, distribution, non-repudiable, etc. • Valid for massive transactions. • Solved mapping of transaction logic to actors and assets through DIDs. • Open APIs to ease integration and development. • Automated instantiation managing onboarding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex setup which requires nodes connectivity. • Not directly generalizable, requires development and custom data model processing. • Difficult to manage onboarding and the logic for governance.

EXTERNAL FACTORS

OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply such registry of trading transactions to other verticals and domains. • Apply DLT technologies to solutions for monetization but not for coins. • Extend the use of machines, not just of human agreements. • Relate to billing systems. • Enable transparent debug and forensics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of technology in different companies and sectors. • Part of standardization in different initiatives with potential compliance requirement as stopper. • Qualified team with relevant skills for other positions. • Existing patents.

4.4.2 Smart Contracts

The SWOT chart of the SC exploitable assets is depicted in Table 4-8.

Table 4-8 SWOT chart of the SC System outcomes

INTERNAL FACTORS

STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key element for the creation of a trusted marketplace for xNFs. • Facilitates trustworthy management of the contracts attached to the xNFs. • Allows executing contracts in an automated way without manual and third-party intervention, cutting down on administration time and service costs. • Increases efficiency of business processes. • Reduces the risk of errors and disputes. • Allows xNF / Service providers to offer their services in a trusted environment. • Provides different stakeholders with access to the catalogue of xNFs / Services of different providers. • Allows placing orders in a secure way. • Eases the creation of offer / order models to developers (SC Dev Toolkit). • Enables the validation of offer / order models before addition to the marketplace (SC Dev Toolkit). • Supports the creation, configuration, and customization of SC states. • Covers the entire digital life cycle of a SC, from negotiation to control and verification of the fulfilment of contractual obligations. • Robust data model to represent a large variety of scenarios. • Application to different kinds of assets (VNFs, edge functions, NSs, Network Slices, etc.). • Able to process alerts and events from external systems. • Interacts with the DLT for offers / orders / SC States modification. • Cloud-native approach. • Microservices Architecture. • Compliance with standards (TM Forum specifications). • Standard K8s-based installation. Stateless component with no high requirement of resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SC Dev Toolkit requires local installation (5MB approximately). • The SC Dev Toolkit do not offer a user-friendly front-end (GUI), just a CLI. • The SC Dev Toolkit do not support the interactive creation of offers/ orders. • Service discovery, which offers a way to find available offers based on an intent, not supported. • The lack of a User Interface (UI) for the marketplace makes more complicated to work with it. • Only one stakeholder's user is possible in each instance of the marketplace. • Certain skills required to develop a SC using the SC Dev Toolkit.

EXTERNAL FACTORS

OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing adoption of blockchain technology. • Need for more secure, efficient, and transparent ways to execute transactions. • Demonstrated potential of blockchain and SCs in various sectors (i.e., supply chain management, real estate, and e-commerce, etc.). • Blockchain is an innovative and revolutionary technology that presents a promising solution to solve the trust problems in future 6G wireless networks. • Blockchain-enabled SCs can guarantee the different terms and conditions of future applications. • SCs are poised to play significant roles in shaping the future of 6G networks by enhancing security, enabling novel services, and transforming network management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Despite the benefits of SCs, there are still security and implementation issues to be solved. • There are also scalability problems associated with blockchain. • Currently, mature standards of verifying SCs are still absent and thus needed. • SCs must comply with relevant laws and regulations to be legally enforceable. • Governments' investment in blockchain technology and SCs is required. • Young technology in its infancy when applied to wireless networks. • Complexity of SC systems and lack of knowledge and understanding among potential users and stakeholders. • Shortage of skilled professionals.
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4.4.3 Smart Discovery

The SWOT chart of the SD exploitable assets is depicted in Table 4-9.

Table 4-9 SWOT chart of the SD outcomes

INTERNAL FACTORS

STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced machine learning algorithms enable personalized and efficient resource recommendations. • Seamless integration with the decentralized marketplace infrastructure enhances accessibility and usability. • Real-time updates and dynamic adaptation capabilities ensure relevance and responsiveness to user needs. • Transparent and trust-based approach utilizing blockchain technology fosters user confidence and participation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliance on accurate and up-to-date data sources for optimal performance may present challenges in certain environments. • Complexity in algorithmic development and maintenance requires ongoing investment in skilled personnel and resources. • Potential scalability issues could arise in highly dynamic and rapidly expanding marketplace ecosystems.

EXTERNAL FACTORS

OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing demand for efficient resource discovery solutions in the telecommunications industry presents significant market expansion opportunities. • Collaboration with third-party developers and service providers can lead to innovative enhancements and feature additions. • Integration with emerging technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT) and edge computing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intense competition from established players and new entrants in the market may erode market share and pricing power. • Rapid technological advancements and shifting market trends may render current algorithms or approaches obsolete if not continually updated.

<p>opens avenues for novel use cases and partnerships.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expansion into adjacent markets or industries seeking similar resource optimization solutions can diversify revenue streams. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Security vulnerabilities or breaches within the blockchain infrastructure could undermine user trust and confidence in the system.
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4.4.4 SLA Assurance

The SWOT chart of the SLA Assurance exploitable assets is depicted in Table 4-10.

Table 4-10 SWOT chart of the SLA Assurance outcomes

INTERNAL FACTORS

STRENGTHS +	WEAKNESSES –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brings actionable data to monitored processes closing the loop. Valid for multiple network managers and NaaS APIs. Solved mapping of captured metrics and policies to control. IoT messaging to ease integration and development of systems based on synchronous information sharing. Forecast values of time series. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex setup, which requires data endpoints connectivity. Not directly generalizable, requires development and custom data and message model processing. Difficult to define application specific policies.

EXTERNAL FACTORS

OPPORTUNITIES +	THREATS –
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply SLA assurance control loops to other verticals and domains. Apply SLA assurance control to solutions where networking has a big impact on QoS. Extend the evidence and issues to all systems, not just to the ones directly involved. Relate to SCADA systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standard technologies and pipelines from different companies and sectors. Part of standardization in different initiatives with potential compliance requirement as stopper. Qualified team with relevant skills for other positions. Existing patents.

4.5 Business Model: Value Proposition Canvas

4.5.1 Distributed Ledger Technologies

The business model canvas of the developed DLT system and the knowledge captured during analysis of alternatives, development and deployment is shown in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-4 Business model canvas of the DLT system

The main exploitation opportunities are related to migrate the solution to other agreements and marketplaces such as the ones to be established by the connectors to data spaces. Accordingly, the value proposition canvas for the DLT system is shown in Figure 4-5 and Figure 4-6.

Figure 4-5 Value proposition canvas of the DLT system (1)

Figure 4-6 Value proposition canvas of the DLT system (2)

4.5.2 Smart Contracts

The value proposition canvas for the SC system is shown in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-7 Value proposition canvas of the SC system

4.5.3 Smart Discovery

The value proposition canvas for the SD system is shown in Figure 4-8.

Product/Outcome: SD System		Customer: CSP	
(Product or Service) Features	Gain Creators	Gains	Customer Jobs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advanced machine learning algorithms for personalized resource recommendations. Real-time updates and dynamic adaptation capabilities. Seamless integration with decentralized marketplace infrastructure. Transparent and trust-based approach utilizing blockchain technology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient resource discovery leading to optimized resource utilization. Enhanced user experience through personalized recommendations. Improved decision-making and agility in accessing relevant resources. Increased trust and confidence in the marketplace ecosystem. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved operational efficiency and resource utilization. Enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty. Increased agility and responsiveness to market demands. Competitive advantage through innovative service offerings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiently discover and access relevant network resources. Ensure optimal resource utilization and allocation. Enhance customer satisfaction through personalized service offerings. Maintain competitiveness in a rapidly evolving market landscape.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of time and effort spent on manual resource searching. Minimization of uncertainty and risk associated with resource selection. Alleviation of concerns regarding data security and trustworthiness. Mitigation of challenges related to resource scarcity and inefficient utilization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-consuming and labor-intensive manual resource discovery processes. Uncertainty and risk associated with selecting suitable resources. Concerns regarding data security and trust in the marketplace ecosystem. Challenges in adapting to changing market dynamics and customer needs. 	

Figure 4-8 Value proposition canvas of the SD system

4.5.4 SLA Assurance

The business model canvas of the developed SLA assurance and the knowledge captured during development, integration and deployment is shown in Figure 4-9.

KEY PARTNERS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring technology developers, Prometheus, Open Telemetry, ELK, InfluxDB, Thanos Data scientists Data spaces initiatives EU regulators Cloud vendors Network operators 	KEY ACTIVITIES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply in relevant scenario to showcase Standard data formats adoption Network abstraction and operation 	VALUE PROPOSITIONS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time series monitoring Forecast values/trends Network assets and configuration abstraction Information sharing between systems through IoT messages Operation of network assets Management of container lifecycle 	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solution provider Consultancy Consortiums 	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliability of extended sensors in connected cars Quality of connectivity in mobility SCADA systems QoS-driven media control Energy-cost monitoring and forecast to plan production when energy is cheaper
COST <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equipment cost Maintenance employees 	KEY RESOURCES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trained technicians Deployment scripts for automation, APIs for network abstraction and policies for metrics Valid SW stack and setup 		CHANNELS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Corporate website Professional social media Technology Transfer staff 	
			REVENUE STREAMS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solution provider Consultancy/Training Maintenance services Patent fees 	

Figure 4-9 Business model canvas of the SLA assurance system

The main exploitation opportunities are related to monitoring solutions of connectivity time series such as the ones running in mobility contexts or KPI-sensible services. Accordingly, the value proposition canvas of the SLA assurance system is shown in Figure 4-10 and Figure 4-11.

Figure 4-10 Value proposition canvas of the SLA assurance system (1)

Figure 4-11 Value proposition canvas of the SLA assurance system (2)

5 Exploitation Plan

This section outlines the exploitation strategy and activities planned by each organization involved in the project, namely Vicomtech, ATOS and i2CAT. It provides insights into how the project outcomes will be leveraged and commercialized to maximize their impact and value. By detailing the planned activities and strategies of each organization, this section offers a roadmap for the effective exploitation of the project results, ensuring that they are effectively translated into tangible benefits for stakeholders and the broader marketplace ecosystem.

5.1 Exploitation Strategy and Activities - Vicomtech

5.1.1 Individual Strategy

The strategy of Vicomtech, anchored by the non-profit foundation nature and the mission from the research centre is to transfer solutions to the industry, based on research and innovation.

Accordingly, Vicomtech has a prominent role in the past and ongoing projects with SMEs and industries in the design on how technologies can meet the problems and requirements of services and products. Thus, once the solution, with a high technology, research or innovation ingredient is validated in simple and isolated scenarios, we package and document solution to be transferred to the client (potentially including owned licenses).

Then, Vicomtech support the technology integration and the application test and adjustments. But as a research centre, we do not provide maintenance or 24x7 support. In the case the client has technological skills the transference is done to the client directly. In the case the results are satisfactory and convincing we transfer the solution to any proposed software factory with the capacity to provide such required services.

This way from the classical application or service development loop, Vicomtech, under the context of projects covers the coloured phases of the Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1 Vicomtech's strategy on solution providing

5.1.2 Joint Exploitation Strategy

Vicomtech is often working in consortiums and collaborative projects and the cooperation context is a natural scenario.

The cooperation of i2CAT and Vicomtech along different projects has created a good symbiosis where Vicomtech, more closed to virtualization and i2CAT more specialized on networking technologies bring complementary expertise to different projects.

This complementarity is being exploited in collaborative projects such as 6G-XR, a 6G-IA SNS project in the context of network enablers for XR experiences and in 6GDIFERENTE, a Red de Excelencia Cervera project in the context of Non-Terrestrial Networks, Edge-Cloud Continuum, advanced radio, and optical features and other foreseen 6G technologies.

The complementarity is positive for collaborative projects and their teams are committed to continue in the future.

This complementarity is often touching the projects results and the possibility to exploit the expertise to support other entities through subcontracting formulas has been discussed and agreed in the past.

5.2 Exploitation Strategy and Activities - ATOS

5.2.1 Organization and Innovation Structure

Eviden is an **Atos Group** company with an annual revenue of c. €5 billion. Eviden is a next-gen technology leader in data-driven, trusted, and sustainable digital transformation with a strong portfolio of patented technologies. With worldwide leading positions in advanced computing, security, AI, cloud, and digital platforms, it provides deep expertise for all industries in more than 47 countries. Bringing together 53,000 world-class talents, Eviden expands the possibilities of data and technology across the digital continuum, now and for generations to come. With a unique ability to bring all these capabilities holistically to our clients through our own Intellectual Property (IP) with 2,100 patents and 50,000 certifications and the IP of our leading partners. While we have a worldwide presence and footprint, we provide strong European sovereign digital capabilities and are recognized as the sole European tier-one manufacturer of high-performance computers, helping public and private organizations meet the highest sovereignty levels in digital security and advanced data processing. Eviden supports clients across seven Industries:

- Energy & Utilities
- Financial Services & Insurance
- Healthcare & Life Sciences
- Manufacturing
- Public Sector & Defense
- Retail, Transport and Logistics
- Telecom, Media & Technology (TMT)

BDS (Big Data & Security) is a specialized division in Eviden that brings together expertise in Big Data, Cybersecurity, and Mission-Critical Systems. It holds the distinction of being the #1 player in Europe and #3 on a global scale in the field of Supercomputing, a significant achievement that showcases its leadership position in

Europe and its strong presence and competitiveness in the worldwide market. The BDS Division is structured in five complementary businesses that help customers build trusted and integrated intelligent systems:

- Cybersecurity services: expertise of cybersecurity professionals to advise, build and operate ongoing up-to-date extreme security.
- Cybersecurity products: highly certified software and hardware products to support customers in protecting their data, managing access, and securing identities, bringing the needed layer of trust in today's heterogenous digital environments.
- Mission Critical Systems (MCS): highly efficient & resilient mission solutions for organizations, which missions include the need for a high focus on safety and security. This includes the protection of nations and populations, protection of exposed workers and the integrity of infrastructures to deliver safe services to populations. MCS addresses particularly the homeland security, defense, telco, aerospace, energy, and transportation sectors.
- High-Performance Computing, Quantum, and AI: High-performance Hardware/Software technologies and services for digital simulation and Artificial Intelligence, enabling public research labs and corporate R&D teams to perform very complex simulation using the most powerful Computing systems in the world, combination of high-end Hardware and software environments optimized for Manufacturing, Weather Forecasts, Life science and Oil and Gas industries.
- Business Computing & AI: uniquely powerful Hardware/Software solutions and services for computing massive business data flows and turning them into business outcomes. Best in class AI computer vision technologies enabling the real time analytics of the most complex data (images) in a highly performant and secure environment.

The division relies on R&D teams whose expertise is recognized internationally and strongly contributes to the development of Eviden technology portfolio, from infrastructures to smart data platforms and industry solutions.

R&D Spain is the source of innovative ideas coming from EU and national research funded projects for the organization. It comprises four main areas, as shown in Figure 5-2.

Figure 5-2 ATOS Big Data & Security division, R&D Spain

- Artificial Intelligence & Business Computing area focuses on developing innovative software solutions and services powered by advanced and innovative Artificial Intelligence techniques.
- Digital Security primarily focuses on developing digital security solutions to protect citizens and organizations and operate in secure and trusted digital

environments for automated AI vision inspection, remote monitoring, and automation.

- **Data Intelligence** area concentrates on data-driven business transformation in economic sectors.
- **Network & Edge** aims to develop innovative solutions for the next generation of networks (beyond 5G and 6G) and edge computing to enable opportunities in vertical industries. This area is further divided into two teams: Edge Computing and Smart Networks.

ATOS team involved in the 6GENABLERS-DLT project is part of **Smart Networks** and includes researchers, technicians, developers, and business consultants that collaborate to booster the impact that research work may have both inside and outside the organization and to find the best way to approach the technological results of R&D projects to the market. In turn, business consultants play the link between R&D and the business area in BDS. In the one hand, business consultants have a general vision about the company strategy and about the main business activities, particularly the BDS ones; on the other hand, they have a general view of all research projects of the R&D Spain department. Therefore, they are key to encouraging the transfer of generated innovative results to the corresponding BDS business lines. The main goal of this structure is to foster and facilitate the innovation process in Eviden to enhance the portfolio of products and technologies offered to our customers.

5.2.2 General Exploitation Strategy and Activities

BDS R&D Spain consider the following general exploitation scenarios for the results coming from their participation in research projects.

- **Knowledge transfer:** Participation in R&D projects helps Eviden to be strategically positioned in the new telecommunications paradigm and be at the forefront of the latest technology, methodologies, and industry trends. Knowledge, although an intangible result from the project, is critical for an organization like Eviden. BDS R&D Spain will make sure that this knowledge is transferred, both internally and externally.

Usual activities to promote knowledge transfer:

- a. **Internally:** Regular meetings with the different BDS business lines, presentations in internal meetings or events, internal publications, etc.
- b. **Externally:** Participation in relevant fora (i.e., events, collaboration with other research projects, webinars, blogs, paper publications, etc.)

- **Technology Transfer:** Whenever possible, the technical outcomes of the project will be presented in different fora for their potential reuse and extension.

Usual activities to promote technology transfer:

- a. **Internally:** Demos in meetings with the different BDS business lines, presentations and demos in internal meetings or events, internal publications, etc.
- b. **Externally:** Presentations/demos in relevant fora (i.e., events, webinars, meetings with other research projects, etc.).

- **Integration in existing and future research projects:** BDS R&D Spain participates regularly in national and European R&I projects with the goal of contributing to strengthen the TMT industry in Spain and Europe. Whenever possible, technical results may be used in future R&I projects in order to improve their sustainability and keep evolving them with the goal to reach the market in the near future.

- **Contribution to standardization:** BDS R&D Spain provides R&D projects all the knowledge and experience acquired thanks to participation in SDOs and open-source communities like Open-Source MANAGEMENT and Orchestration (MANO) (OSM). BDS R&D Spain follows the activity of this type of organizations with the goal of being aware of those topics that may be of interest for the projects and, vice versa, giving visibility of the work being done by the projects. The final purpose is fostering collaboration and increasing the possibility of influencing the community whenever possible.
- **Enhancement of the Eviden portfolio:** Results from the R&D EU projects play a vital role in Eviden enhancing the portfolio of products, services and technologies offered to its customers. Eviden will use the knowledge and the expertise and, whenever possible, the technical outcomes resulting from the project for evolving the BDS portfolio and adapting it to the new cloud native paradigm. For this purpose, there is an internal process to accelerate that those assets* coming from R&D projects with the most business potential are evolved in order to become part of the organization portfolio.

*Note: BDS R&D Spain defines an asset as any project outcome owned partially or totally by the organization which can be reusable and exploitable, where:

- reusable means that something can be easily used again in a future project or in a commercial solution,
- and exploitable means that it can be monetized as product, service, or consultancy.

5.2.3 SC System-specific Exploitation Plan

In this context, BDS R&D foresees the following exploitation scenarios as the most suitable for its Key Exploitable Result, the SC System, that will be further explored during the project lifetime.

- **Knowledge transfer:** BDS R&D Spain will make sure that the knowledge acquired during its participation in the project is transferred, both internally and externally.
 - a) Activities planned within the organization:
 1. Publication of project activities and results in the BDS R&D Spain Internal Newsletter.
 2. Publication of the project in the BDS R&D Public Booklet: [Smart Networks | BDS R&D Spain \(evidenresearch.eu\)](https://evidenresearch.eu).
 3. Presentation of the project activities and results in internal meetings or events, such as the Innovation week.
 - b) Activities planned outside the organization:
 4. Presentation of the project activities and results in relevant fora.
 5. Collaboration with other research projects.
 6. Publication of blogs.
- **Technology Transfer:** BDS R&D Spain, whenever possible, will promote that the technical outcomes of the project are reused.
 - a) Activities planned within the organization:
 7. Demos to the BDS business lines potentially interested in the technical outcomes.
 - b) Activities planned outside the organization:

8. Presentations/demos in relevant fora (i.e., meetings with other research projects).
- **Integration in research projects:**
 9. Participation in new research projects where the technical outcomes of the project can be presented as background IP contribution.
- **Enhancement of the Eviden portfolio:** The knowledge and the expertise acquired during our participation in the project and, whenever possible, the resulting technical outcomes will be used for evolving the BDS portfolio via the internal promotion of knowledge / technology transfer.
 10. At the end of the project, the technical results won't have the maturity needed for their inclusion in the organization's portfolio, so we plan to evolve the SC System via participation in other research projects.
 11. In addition, we plan to connect the SC System with another asset of the unit (i.e., xNF repository) for expanding its functionality and make the asset even more attractive. These functionalities will increase the reliability, trust, and resilience of virtualized environments, which ultimately leads to faster and higher adoption of 6G technologies.

This exploitation plan is supported by a sound communication campaign (as described in deliverable E7.1) to be executed during the project lifetime and beyond with the main goal of raising awareness and engaging with stakeholders, both externally as well as internally in our own company.

5.3 Exploitation Strategy and Activities - i2CAT

5.3.1 Innovation and Exploitation Vision

As a prominent entity within the European research landscape, i2CAT is dedicated to fostering innovation among European enterprises. Embracing the Open Innovation approach and transitioning from the triple Helix to the quadruple Helix model, we are committed to leveraging outcomes from R&D initiatives. Drawing from extensive experience and knowledge acquired through numerous European-funded projects, we prioritize the accumulation of intellectual capital.

Collaborating closely with universities, i2CAT serves as a research center facilitating continuous knowledge transfer to future generations of experts. This is achieved through workshops, courses, and scholarships offered to university students. Additionally, our contribution extends to scientific societies, where we publish articles in esteemed and internationally recognized journals and conferences, including IEEE GLOBECOM, IEEE ICC, EuCNC, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies, and IEEE Communications Letters.

With a vision to attain a leading role in ICT research and innovation, i2CAT places a special emphasis on addressing market needs. Our ambition is to emerge as a globally acknowledged strategic partner spearheading Internet initiatives across economic, industrial, and social domains, thereby enhancing innovation and technology transfer competitiveness. Bolstering our industrial footprint, our board of trustees comprises key players in the telecom industry such as Cisco, Juniper, Cellnex, Mediapro, Telefonica and Vodafone, among others.

Our overall strategy involves patenting and licensing the outcomes of research and innovation endeavors, either through established companies or potentially via the creation of spinoffs capable of further developing and exploiting generated knowledge and prototypes. Simultaneously, recognizing the novelty of our endeavors, we aim to disseminate results through participation in scientific forums, disseminating articles in relevant journals or presenting at conferences.

5.3.2 Project-specific Exploitation Plan

In the framework of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, i2CAT has devised a comprehensive plan for exploitation and dissemination activities to leverage the project's outcomes effectively.

Firstly, i2CAT intends to capitalize on the results of scientific activities conducted within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project by publishing them and integrating them into its internal assets portfolio. By disseminating these results industrially, i2CAT aims to advance their evolution and promote their adoption among relevant stakeholders.

Furthermore, i2CAT recognizes the importance of regularly presenting the outcomes of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project to key industrial partners to raise awareness and influence the trajectory of technological evolution. Given that the project aligns with 5GBarcelona, a regional initiative aimed at establishing a 5G ecosystem and promoting SME innovation, i2CAT views the project as instrumental in achieving 5GBarcelona goals. Leveraging the outcomes of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, i2CAT aims to solidify its position as a pivotal technological partner in the 5G domain and contribute to the development of an advanced ecosystem within the 5G innovation hub.

Additionally, i2CAT plans to include the developed technologies in upcoming proposals, leveraging the insights and innovations generated through the 6GENABLERS-DLT project to fuel future collaborative endeavors. By fostering collaboration and partnerships within research communities, industrial sectors, and citizen users, i2CAT aims to design and spearhead a range of follow-up research projects and initiatives at both national and international levels, further advancing the domains of 5G/6G and Cybersecurity.

6 Overall Assessment of the Project Impact

This section offers an overall evaluation of the project's impact, focusing on the Target Business Indicators and Key Value Indicators (KVI) associated with each system comprising the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. By analyzing these indicators, we gain insights into the project's effectiveness in achieving its goals and driving tangible outcomes.

6.1 Target Business Indicators

Table 6-1 compiles Vicomtech's anticipated impact on the business opportunities arising from the DLT developed solutions.

Table 6-1 Impact on business opportunities of DLT technology-based outcomes

Description	Impact
Transfer to companies	Technologies transferred to 2 clients (2024 – 2025)
Technology ingredient to national project	Technologies applied to 2 projects (2024 – 2025)
Technology skilled	2 Papers (1 conference + 1 journal) (2024 – 2025)
Demo to clients	Technology showcase to visitors/potential clients (5-6 per year)
Showcase to marketing staff	Aggregation to technology portfolio

Table 6-2 summarizes ATOS's anticipated impact on the business opportunities arising from the SC outcomes.

Table 6-2 Impact on business opportunities of SC outcomes

Description	Impact
Knowledge Transfer	≥ 4 dissemination activities inside / outside the organization in period 2024-2025
Technology Transfer	≥2 demos inside / outside the organization in period 2024-2025
Technology ingredient to National /European R&D projects	Technologies applied to ≥ 1 projects in period 2024-2025
Showcase to BDS business lines	Evolution of the asset for potential future integration in portfolio

Table 6-3 summarizes i2CAT's anticipated impact on the business opportunities arising from the SD outcomes.

Table 6-3 Impact on business opportunities of SD outcomes

Description	Impact
Knowledge Transfer	≥ 3 dissemination activities inside / outside the organization in period 2024-2025
Technology Transfer	≥2 demos inside / outside the organization in period 2024-2025
Technology ingredient to National /European R&D proposals	Technologies included in ≥ 1 proposals in period 2024-2025
Showcase to business departments for asset discovery process	Evolution of the asset for potential future integration in portfolio

Table 6-4 compiles Vicomtech’s anticipated impact on the business opportunities arising from the SLA assurance developed solutions.

Table 6-4 Impact on business opportunities of SLA assurance outcomes

Description	Impact
Transfer to companies	Technologies transferred to 2 clients (2024 – 2025)
Technology ingredient to national project	Technologies applied to 2 projects (2024 – 2025)
Technology skilled	2 Papers (2 conferences) (2024 – 2025)
Demo to clients	Technology showcase to visitors/potential clients (5-6 per year)
Showcase to marketing staff	Aggregation to technology portfolio

6.2 Key Value Indicators

Key Value Indicators (KVI) from Smart Networks and Services (SNS) programme [34] are essential topics to be considered in the assessment of project outcomes. In this regard, the following tables outline the impact of the project results on the considered KVI, namely: sustainability, trustworthiness, dependability, flexibility inclusiveness and acceptance.

Table 6-5 indicates how the DLT developed solutions relate to the considered KVI.

Table 6-5 KVI for DLT technology-based outcomes

Description	Impact
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced time to negotiation. Pay as you go business models fostering thin deployments and energy efficiency. Use of virtualization/softwarization and cloud-native approach to decouple from specific HW.
Trustworthiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immutable, transparent, and non-repudiable agreements. Local node APIs to operate with the platform.
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distributed infrastructure not depending on central services or infrastructures.
Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dynamic agreements and smart contract lifecycles as part of adaptive policies or protocols. Reuse of unused/available assets promoting circular economy.
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrol effective, accountable and transparent actors at all levels.
Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Governance not controlled by a specific entity or lobby applying policies or rules.

Table 6-6 showcases the impact of SC outcomes on the considered KVI.

Table 6-6 KVI for SC outcomes

Description	Impact
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guaranteed terms and conditions of future applications in complex 6G networks. Increased efficiency and transparency of business processes. Automation of processes.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased security, reduced risk, and mitigation of fraud. • Time and cost reduction. • Resource sharing.
Trustworthiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust environment for business transactions. • Trustworthy management of the contracts attached to the xNFs.
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic contracts execution, with no manual and third-party intervention.
Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large variety of business scenarios. • Easy integration in larger infrastructures. • Nor manual nor third-party intervention.
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SC development more accessible to a broader range of users, including those without extensive technical knowledge. • Fostering collaboration.
Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud-native approach, microservices architecture, and align with latest standards.

Table 6-7 showcases the impact of SD outcomes on the considered KVIs.

Table 6-7 KVIs for SD outcomes

Description	Impact
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimize resource utilization and reduces wastage. • Promote sustainable practices within the marketplace. • Enable resource sharing.
Trustworthiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverages transparent and trust-based approaches, such as blockchain technology. • Fosters trust among participants through personalized recommendations and transparent record-keeping.
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offers real-time updates and dynamic adaptation capabilities. • Consistently delivers accurate and relevant resource recommendations, reducing uncertainty.
Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables seamless integration with the decentralized marketplace infrastructure. • Facilitates agility and adaptability to changing business needs by providing access to resources across diverse network environments.
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides equal access to resources for all participants within the marketplace ecosystem. • Ensures that users of varying backgrounds and expertise can effectively engage with the platform.
Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addresses pain points associated with resource discovery, such as manual processes and uncertainty. • Enhances acceptance and adoption among marketplace participants by providing a seamless and intuitive experience.

Table 6-8 indicates how the SLA assurance solutions relate to the considered KVIs.

Table 6-8 KVIs for SLA assurance outcomes

Description	Impact
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced time to react and prevent. • Use of virtualization/softwarization and cloud-native approach to decouple from specific hardware.
Trustworthiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues are reported in IoT messaging data bus to foster transparency.
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable business models fostering awareness and penalties if SLAs are not satisfied.

Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Policies can be customized and loaded.
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Enrol effective, accountable and transparent actors at all levels.
Acceptance	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Integration with de-facto industry standards such as Prometheus.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, this document has provided a comprehensive analysis of the market and business opportunities presented by the technologies developed within the 6GENABLERS-DLT project.

Beginning with a thorough market analysis, the document delves into the evolving landscape of 6G networks, highlighting the role of emerging technologies such as Blockchain and Smart Contracts in meeting the stringent demands of future networks.

Subsequently, a detailed business analysis of the various systems is undertaken, employing widely used tools such as SWOT analysis and the Value Proposition Canvas. This analysis offers valuable insights into the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the project's outcomes, as well as the value proposition they offer to customers.

Furthermore, an initial exploitation plan is outlined, accompanied by a description of the activities planned by each participating organization to ensure the successful implementation of the strategy. These activities are aimed at leveraging the project results effectively, fostering collaboration, and driving innovation within the industry.

Lastly, an overall assessment of the project's impact is conducted, shedding light on the anticipated benefits and outcomes of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project. Through this comprehensive analysis, the document provides a roadmap for maximizing the project's potential and realizing its objectives in the dynamic landscape of future wireless networks.

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